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ABSTRACT

This work reports on a method to open nanoscale gaps in h-shaped graphene nano-constrictions by electrical breakdown at room temperature and pressure below 10^{-5} mbar. The method was validated on 275 devices, fabricated on eight different chips, using Chemical Vapor Deposition (CVD)-grown graphene from in-house production and from two commercial sources. The gap width was estimated by fitting the I–V traces after electrical breakdown with the Simmons model for the intermediate-voltage range. The statistics on the collected data demonstrates that the method results in normally distributed nanoscale gaps in h-shaped graphene nano-constrictions, with an estimated average width centered around 1 nm and a gap fabrication yield of 95%.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Tunnel junctions as sensing platforms and nanoscale electrodes for low-dimensional and quantum devices rely on fabrication methods capable of opening nanoscale gaps in low-dimensional conductors.^{1–4} Graphene is an ideal candidate as a nanoscale electrode to contact organic matter due to its intrinsic ability to form π - π stacking and van der Waals bonds.⁵ Examples of applications of graphene nanoscale electrodes include molecular junctions,⁶ graphene nanoribbons,⁷ and DNA sequencing devices.¹ Different techniques and setups have been proposed and employed so far to open nanoscale gaps in graphene, including electron beam lithography,⁸ focused ion and electron beam milling,^{9,10} electrical breakdown,^{11–13} selective hydrogen plasma etching,³ and scanning probe methods.¹⁴ Among them, the electrical breakdown can be engineered to fabricate very narrow gaps (~ 1 nm wide) without requiring particularly advanced electron or ion beam-based facilities, nor scanning probe setups, all intrinsically sequential and therefore with limited potential for upscaling. This work describes a method and an experimental setup that can be implemented with

common laboratory electrical equipment to fabricate nanoscale gaps in h-shaped graphene nano-constrictions by feedback-controlled electrical breakdown.¹³ The method is potentially upscalable, has a gap formation yield of 95%, and was proven reproducible from a statistics across 275 devices, including eight different chips, each representative of a different fabrication batch, and graphene from three different sources, both commercially available and internally grown by Chemical Vapor Deposition (CVD). The collected data show that the electrical power that initiates the electrical breakdown is normally distributed around 10 mW, with a variability of about 2 mW between devices fabricated using graphene from different sources. Similarly, the gap width, estimated by fitting the I–V tunneling traces after electrical breakdown with the Simmons model for the intermediate-voltage range, is normally distributed and centered around 1 nm, with sub-nm variability between devices fabricated using graphene from different sources.

In the following, Sec. II describes the physical principle behind the technique, the device architecture, and the experimental setup. Then, Sec. III describes the procedure adopted to validate the method, with a statistical analysis on the collected data. Finally,

FIG. 1. SEM image (2 kV, 5 μ A) of a representative device. Two platinum electrodes in a four-wire configuration contact the *h*-shaped graphene constriction in the center. Two additional electrodes, symmetrically arranged on the right and left sides of the device, are fabricated for purposes other than the electrical breakdown. Their function is not described here as it goes beyond the scope of this work.

Sec. IV summarizes the main results of this work. The device fabrication process, the graphene growth procedure, and additional electrical data are shown in the [supplementary material](#).

II. METHOD

A. Principle

The method proposed in this work is based on the following physical principle: by forcing an increasing current in an *h*-shaped graphene nano-constriction under high vacuum ($<10^{-5}$ mbar), the constriction undergoes self-heating due to the Joule effect until the energy dissipated within the constriction is sufficient to activate the sublimation of carbon atoms. The sublimation process can start from either (i) weakly bound carbon atoms occupying sites at the edges of the film or at grain boundaries, where the film resistance is higher due to electron scattering and where the binding energy is

much less (<10 eV) than that of an atom occupying a site in a perfect lattice (~ 30 eV),¹⁵ or (ii) atoms occupying sites in a perfect lattice at the center of the constriction, where the temperature profile reaches its maximum due to the Joule effect.¹⁶ In both cases, the sublimation then proceeds to the now loosely bound neighboring atoms and so on, forming a gap that extends all the way across the constriction. The electrical continuity of the film is therefore interrupted, and the current flowing is limited by electron tunneling through the gap. The process is done in a controlled environment with a low oxygen concentration, in vacuum with a pressure below 10^{-5} mbar, in order to limit carbon oxidation and assure that the electrical breakdown is dominated by sublimation.¹⁷ The possibility of carbon oxidation involving oxygen atoms from the SiO_2 substrate has been ruled out by previous experiments.¹⁷

In practice, the method consists in driving a current through a graphene nano-constriction by slowly increasing the voltage across the constriction and by monitoring its resistance in real time. When the resistance reaches very large values, typically in the $100 \text{ M}\Omega$ – $1 \text{ G}\Omega$ range and above, the voltage is rapidly swept back to zero. The procedure is then repeated to verify that the resistance does not further change and therefore assess the formation of the gap.

B. Device

The geometry of the graphene constriction can be diverse, e.g., triangular or hourglass-shaped or *h*-shaped. The *h*-shaped constriction allows to fabricate nanoscale gaps within a well-defined region, and therefore, it was chosen as the reference geometry for this work. [Figure 1](#) shows an SEM image of a representative device before electrical breakdown. The graphene constriction is about 400 nm wide and 800 nm long, fabricated on a Si/SiO_2 substrate, and contacted by platinum electrodes. The device fabrication process is thoroughly described in the [supplementary material](#).

C. Setup

The electrical breakdown setup consists of (i) one Digital to Analog Converter (DAC) to generate the voltage across the device,

FIG. 2. Photograph of the vacuum chamber with a view on a chip and electrical schematic of the experimental setup. $A_{V/V}$ and $A_{I/V}$ are the voltage amplifier and the transimpedance amplifier, respectively.

(ii) one voltage amplifier to amplify the output of the DAC, (iii) one low-noise transimpedance amplifier to convert the current into a measurable voltage, (iv) one Analog to Digital Converter (ADC) to read the voltage at the output of the transimpedance amplifier, and (v) one probe station, with at least two probes, which can operate in vacuum, at room temperature.

The data shown in this work were collected from a Lakeshore probe station (CRX-6.5 K) operating under vacuum ($\sim 10^{-5}$ mbar) at room temperature using an AdWin Gold II ADC-DAC unit operating at 450 kHz with internal averaging of 9000 points, corresponding to an effective sampling frequency of 50 Hz and a voltage sweep rate of 0.3 V/s, a voltage amplifier Basel HV-Amplifier SP 908, and a low-noise transimpedance amplifier Femto DLPCA-200. The ADC-DAC was controlled via Matlab. It is worth observing that since the Joule heat dissipated in the graphene constriction depends also on the constriction geometry, the experimental parameters of the setup, such as the voltage sweep rate and the DAC-ADC operating frequency, were tuned for the specific geometry in use. Figure 2 shows the electrical schematic of the experimental setup and a photograph of the vacuum chamber with a view on a chip.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The method was validated on 275 devices fabricated at the cleanroom facilities of the Binnig and Rohrer Nanotechnology

Center (BRNC) using graphene from three different sources. In detail, 216 devices were fabricated on five different chips using two different batches of graphene grown by CVD at Empa (herein referred to as *group A*; the growth procedure is described in the [supplementary material](#)). For comparison, 43 additional devices were fabricated on two different chips using commercial graphene from ANL (herein referred to as *group B*), and 16 additional devices were fabricated on a single chip using commercial graphene from Graphenea (herein referred to as *group C*). Differences in population numbers are due to graphene availability. All chips were fabricated separately from each other, between November 2019 and July 2020, and stored in N_2 for a different amount of time (from days to months) before electrical breakdown. Therefore, each chip is representative of a different fabrication batch.

Figures 3(a) and 3(b) show the AFM images (intensity and phase) of a representative graphene nano-constriction after electrical breakdown. While the narrower part of the gap can hardly be resolved, the larger part of the gap is clearly visible in both the intensity and phase images. The intensity image shows that the apparent thickness of graphene in the constriction is on the average smaller. This is due to the cleaning that takes place during the voltage sweep: the graphene constriction heats up because of the Joule effect and resists residuals, and impurities migrate toward cooler areas, i.e., where the graphene section is larger.¹⁸

FIG. 3. (a) and (b) AFM images of a representative graphene nano-constriction after electrical breakdown. The larger part of the gap is clearly visible in both the intensity (a) and phase (b) images, while the narrower part can hardly be resolved due to spatial resolution. The effect of the surface cleaning due to self-heating during the voltage sweep is also clearly visible as a variation in the graphene apparent thickness. (c) I-V trace of a representative graphene nano-constriction and (d) histogram plot of the resistance before electrical breakdown. (e) I-V trace of a representative graphene nano-constriction and (f) histogram plot of the resistance after electrical breakdown at 3 V. The IV trace after electrical breakdown is fitted with the Simmons model using the parameters $A = 8 \text{ nm}^2$, $\phi_0 = 2.90 \text{ eV}$, and $\Delta s = 1.00 \text{ nm}$.

Figures 3(c) and 3(e) show the I–V trace of a representative graphene nano-constriction before and after electrical breakdown (refer to the [supplementary material](#) for the I–V traces of all 275 devices fabricated in this work). On the one hand, the I–V trace before electrical breakdown is linear, and the resistance of the graphene constriction can be estimated with a linear fit. On the other hand, the I–V trace after electrical breakdown displays the typical *s*-shaped tunneling characteristics, confirming the formation of the gap. The observation of gate-independent I–V tunneling traces at low temperature (see the [supplementary material](#)) provides further evidence of gap formation. An estimate of the gap size was obtained by fitting the I–V traces after electrical breakdown with the Simmons model for the intermediate-voltage range,^{19,20}

$$J = J_0 \left[\left(\varphi_0 - \frac{eV}{2} \right) \exp \left(-\alpha \sqrt{\varphi_0 - \frac{eV}{2}} \right) - \left(\varphi_0 + \frac{eV}{2} \right) \exp \left(-\alpha \sqrt{\varphi_0 + \frac{eV}{2}} \right) \right],$$

where $\varphi_0 > eV/2$ is the effective barrier height; V is the externally applied voltage; $\alpha = \sqrt{2m}4\pi\beta\Delta s/h$; $J_0 = Ae/(2\pi h\beta^2\Delta s^2)$; A is the area of the barrier; $\beta \cong 1$; Δs is the width of the gap; m and e are the mass and the electric charge of a free electron, respectively; and h is the Planck constant. It is worth observing that the Simmons model was originally developed for 3D systems consisting of a thin insulating layer separating two electrodes.¹⁹ The extension of the Simmons model to gaps in 2D materials, and specifically to this work, is not straightforward as the actual gap width typically varies irregularly from one edge of the constriction to the other. In addition, while the gap width obtained by fitting the I–V trace after electrical breakdown using the Simmons model is a convenient metric to compare methods, one should be careful in interpreting this fitting parameter as the actual gap width. The fit was carried out using a wrapper around `scipy.optimize.least_squares`²¹ by simultaneously fitting (i) the tunneling area in the interval from 0.01 nm² (about one atom wide) to 8 nm² (about 20% of the entire constriction section), (ii) the barrier height in the interval from 1.5 eV (minimum value that satisfies the condition $\varphi_0 > eV/2$) to 5.0 eV (graphite's work function), and (iii) the gap width in the interval from 0.1 nm to 5.0 nm. The fitting algorithm tended to maximize the area regardless of the choice of boundaries. However, since the fitted gap and barrier height were found quite insensitive to the tunneling area, the upper bound to the area was set equal to 20% of the constriction section, in agreement with what experimentally observed by AFM. While one would expect φ_0 to be close, if not equal to the work function of graphene, i.e., 4.2 eV, previous works demonstrate that the graphene work function strongly depends on doping, impurities, and gating, with deviations from the theoretical value from a few meV to up to 1 eV and more.^{22–24} Therefore, one can expect the effective barrier height to deviate significantly from the work function value of nominal graphene. This deviation was well accounted for by the choice of bounds, which allowed for the fit to return φ_0 values much lower than any value previously predicted and/or experimentally measured.²² The fitting was considered unreliable and therefore discarded from the dataset used for the statistical analysis of the gap

width described in the following: if the barrier height was smaller than 2.5 eV or if the gap width was larger than 5.0 nm. In fact, in the former case, the barrier height would be most likely physically unrealistic, and in the latter case, the tunneling current would be much lower than that experimentally observed in the voltage range from –3 to +3 V. This data filtering resulted in a subpopulation for the statistical analysis of the gap width consisting of 158 of 216 devices fabricated with graphene from group A, 15 of 43 devices fabricated with graphene from group B, and five of 16 devices fabricated with graphene from group C. A representative I–V tunneling trace generated with the Simmons model using the fitted parameters $A = 8 \text{ nm}^2$, $\varphi_0 = 2.90 \text{ eV}$, and $\Delta s = 1.00 \text{ nm}$ is superimposed to the experimental data in Fig. 3(e).

Figures 3(d) and 3(f) show the histogram plots of the electrical resistance of graphene constriction before (d) and after (f) electrical breakdown. The former is calculated by linearly fitting the electrical breakdown traces between 0 and 200 mV, while the latter is calculated by taking the ratio between the voltage and the current after electrical breakdown at 3 V. The yield of gap formation is defined by considering the fraction of devices that show an *s*-shaped I–V tunneling characteristic after electrical breakdown. This corresponds to about 100% of devices from group A, about 50% of devices from group B, and 100% of devices from group C, with an overall yield of about 95%.

Figure 4 shows a statistical analysis of the electrical breakdown data, grouped by the graphene source. In detail, Fig. 4(a) shows the I–V traces of three representative devices (one for each graphene source), recorded in vacuum, at room temperature, with a voltage sweep rate of 0.3 V/s. On the average, the I–V traces display a similar non-linear behavior: they start approximately linear, and then, a first kink is observed between 5 and 10 V, likely due to the migration of contaminants (which function as graphene dopants via defect formation) from the graphene constriction because of self-heating, followed by a second sharp kink above 15 V, where the current suddenly drops to zero.¹⁸ The voltage is automatically swept back to zero after the second kink where the resistance of the constriction increases significantly. All 275 electrical breakdown I–V traces are shown in the [supplementary material](#). Relevant information on the method implementation can be drawn from the electrical breakdown conditions, i.e., the power (or current) and voltage where the gap is formed. Figure 4(b) shows a power vs voltage scatter plot at the electrical breakdown of 45 randomly selected representative devices, 15 from each graphene group, color-coded by graphene. Figures 4(c) and 4(e) show a box and histogram plot of the power at electrical breakdown, respectively. The power at electrical breakdown is normally distributed with the mean and standard deviations of $8.02 \pm 2.13 \text{ mW}$ (group A), $10.58 \pm 0.46 \text{ mW}$ (group B), and $8.86 \pm 4.04 \text{ mW}$ (group C). Since the higher the mobility, the lower the Joule heat dissipated in the constriction, the power at electrical breakdown and the graphene mobility should correlate for ultra-clean graphene fabricated under identical conditions. However, the large spread of mobility data (refer to the [supplementary material](#)), most likely due to device fabrication variability, which is responsible for unintentional doping and/or defect formation, does not allow us to establish any correlation between the two. Figures 4(d) and 4(f) show a box and histogram plot of the gap width estimated with the Simmons model fit. The analysis is limited to the subpopulation consisting of all experimental I–V traces successfully fitted,

FIG. 4. Statistical analysis of the electrical breakdown data grouped by the graphene source. (a) Representative I–V traces of the electrical breakdown. (b) Scatter plot of electrical power vs voltage at electrical breakdown. (c) Box plot of electrical power at electrical breakdown. (d) Box plot of the gap width obtained by fitting the experimental data with the Simmons model. The analysis on the gap width [(d) and (f)] is limited to the subpopulation consisting of all experimental I–V traces successfully fitted with the Simmons model.

with fitting parameters within the aforementioned boundary conditions. The distribution of the fitted gap width is less obvious than the distribution of the power at electrical breakdown although it tends to resemble a normal distribution. In detail, the mean and

standard deviation of the gap width are 0.93 ± 0.12 nm (group A), 0.96 ± 0.04 nm (group B), and 0.97 ± 0.06 nm (group C). [Table I](#) reports the mean and standard deviations of all fitting parameters, grouped by the graphene source. Remarkably, despite the

TABLE I. Area (A), barrier height (ϕ_0), and gap width (d) obtained by fitting the IV traces after electrical breakdown, grouped by the graphene source.

Group	Population	A (nm ²)	ϕ_0 (eV)	d (nm)
A	158	7.75 ± 1.31	3.04 ± 0.33	0.93 ± 0.12
B	15	8.00 ± 0.00	3.02 ± 0.12	0.96 ± 0.04
C	5	7.98 ± 0.04	2.79 ± 0.17	0.97 ± 0.06

variability in the mobility data, the mean values of all parameters are very similar.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This work reported on a method to fabricate nanoscale gaps in 400 nm wide and 800 nm long *h*-shaped graphene nanoconstrictions by electrical breakdown. The method was validated on a set of 275 devices, including eight different chips and three different types of graphene sources, both in-house CVD grown and commercially available for comparison, with a gap fabrication yield of 95%. The method provided normally distributed nanoscale gaps, with the widths of 0.93 ± 0.12 nm (group A), 0.96 ± 0.04 nm (group B), and 0.97 ± 0.06 nm (group C), as estimated by fitting the electrical breakdown IV traces with the Simmons model. The electrical power at electrical breakdown was also found to be normally distributed with the mean and standard deviation of 8.02 ± 2.13 mW (group A), 10.58 ± 0.46 mW (group B), and 8.86 ± 4.04 mW (group C). While the power at electrical breakdown did not correlate with the mobility data, most likely due to device fabrication variability, which is responsible for unintentional doping and/or defect formation, the variability on mobility does not have a significant influence on the gap fabrication and on the distribution of the gap width. This supports the effectiveness and robustness of the methodology proposed in this work, making it attractive for a variety of purposes, e.g., sensing devices based on tunneling junctions and molecular electronics.

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

See the [supplementary material](#) for a description of the device fabrication process, a description of the graphene growth procedure, all electrical breakdown and tunneling I–V traces, and a statistical analysis of the graphene mobility.

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AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

Author Contributions

O.S. and D.B. equally contributed to this work.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding authors upon reasonable request.

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